

IMPACT A STUDY OF COVID 19 PANDEMIC IMPACT ON ONLINE BUYING OF DOMESTIC PRODUCTS IN KALYAN DOMBIVLI AREA

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Abstract:

Due closure of retail stores, because of lockdown and consumers' concern over getting infected to corona virus in public resulted into drastic increase in online trade.

To stop the spread of COVID-19, the Indian government implemented a stringent national lockdown on March 24, 2020. The 12-week lockdown caused severe impact on daily routine of all individuals. Later many small lockdowns and restrictions also had a great impact on daily life style of people.

The two main strategies used to counteract the effects of the corona virus were social withdrawal and isolation. People all throughout the world have been avoiding public spaces because certain countries are on lockdown and businesses are closed.

The present paper aims at studying the impact of COVID-19 on daily necessities and consumption pattern in Kalyan Dombivli Municipal Corporation Area of Maharashtra.

Key Words: *COVID-19, necessities, Consumption pattern, Online Buying*

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Introduction:

There is fundamental change in the world of business due to Covid pandemic. About two years have passed since the corona virus epidemic prompted many Indian customers to go into lockdown mode as COVID-19 swept quickly across the nation. Online purchases of necessities were flooded by customers, driving ecommerce sales to record levels. Due closure of retail stores, because of lockdown and consumers' concern over getting infected to corona virus in public resulted into drastic increase in online trade.

To stop the spread of COVID-19, the Indian government implemented a stringent national lockdown on March 24, 2020. The 12-week lockdown caused severe impact on daily routine of all individuals. Later many small lockdowns and restrictions also had a great impact on daily life style of people.

The two main strategies used to counteract the effects of the coronavirus were social withdrawal and isolation. People all throughout the world have been avoiding public spaces because certain countries are on lockdown and businesses are closed. The study explores about the rapid use of internet, mobile, etc.in lockdown that imposed in the country. Online shopping is now a days considered to be the most convenient way of shopping to get away free from the spreading virus and keep ourselves in safe and secure environment. People's shopping habits have drastically changed during pandemic period, As a result, limited but necessary buying for necessities is becoming into the new norm, is

becoming into the new norm, from bulk purchasing to online shopping.

The present paper aims at studying the impact of COVID-19 on daily necessities and consumption pattern in Kalyan Dombivli Municipal Corporation Area of Maharashtra. The main purpose of this study is to investigate if the corona virus has pushed people to do online shopping and will they continue doing online shopping when this plague is over. The data for this paper has been collected by circulating questionnaire on the social media.

The aim of this report is to know if the corona virus is pushing people to do online shopping besides this, it is also examined in this study that if people will continue buying products online with the same rate in future when corona virus is over.

Research Methodology:

The research conducted for studying the impact of COVID-19 on daily necessities and consumption pattern in Kalyan Dombivli Municipal Corporation Area of Maharashtra is based on both primary and secondary data. Primary data is collected through structured questionnaire. Secondary data has been obtained from various published sources. The sample size is 50. The respondents were chosen from residents in Kalyan Dombivli area. The methods used is simple random sampling. Data has been analysed and studied with the help of statistical tools such as graph, charts, diagram and other convenient statistical methods.

Data Analysis & Interpretations;

1. From total sample size of 50, there 36 are female respondents and 14 male respondents..
2. The education level of the respondents was less than Graduate-8, Graduate 36 and post graduate or above 06 respondents.
3. The sample can be classified on the basis of age group as Below 20 years 12 respondents, between 21 to 40 there are 29 respondents and in a age group of 41 to 60 there are 07 respondents whereas only 2 respondents are from age group of 60 and above.
4. The change in buying behaviour for different categories of products belonging to necessities showed following

Table 1.1

Table showing product wise shift in buying habits

Product Category	Total % of online buying before pandemic	Total % of online buying after pandemic
Groceries	12%	89%
Perishables(Vegetables & Fruits)	02%	86%
Dairy Products	05%	64%
Medical Necessities	01%	15%
Sanitary Products	07%	92%

Graph 1.1

From the above graph, there is sharp increase in case of Groceries and alike items, perishables, dairy products, medical necessities and sanitary products. The major reasons behind was pandemic fear among people.

Table 1.2

Table showing estimate of product wise shift in buying habits in Post pandemic

Product Category	Total % of online buying after pandemic	Total % of Consumer willing to continue online buying after pandemic
Groceries	89%	42%
Perishables(Vegetables & Fruits)	86%	58%
Dairy Products	64%	70%
Medical Necessities	15%	3%
Sanitary Products	92%	58%

Graph 1.2

Graph showing estimate of product wise shift in buying habits in Post pandemic

Interpretations:

1) Consumers, who are willing to continue online buying after pandemic have different choices for different products. 70% respondents are favorable to continue with dairy products but for medical products it is only 3%

Electronic International Interdisciplinary Research Journal

Volume-X, Issues-VI

Nov - Dec, 2021

- 2) The average choice towards online shopping of domestic domestic product was sanitary products & perishable products.
- 3) Even after pandemic is under control, sizeable consumers are still preferring to buy groceries online.

Findings:

- 1) Before covid 19 pandemic online shopping was not a popular method of buying domestic products
- 2) People mostly prefer buying products by going physically in markets rather than buying online it is because of various reasons and the prominent reason from them is concerns of quality of products that people buy online this is what insist them buying physically
- 3) Although there are several advantages of online shopping like less expensive, time saving etc. but they are quality conscious
- 4) During pandemic, due to lockdowns, social distancing and fear of getting infected there was a drastic shift
- 5) After the Pandemic situation is under control, E-Commerce is a still choice of many consumers of domestic products
- 6) Many discounts & offers in online shopping attracts consumers towards it

Conclusion:

Pandemic has pushed consumers out of physical markets towards online markets. This new experience has created distinct dimensions to shopping habits of people.

It is also observed that, a large portion of consumers is interested in continuing with online shopping due to exciting offers, discounts, saving in time & energy of shopping & ease of shopping.

References:

- COVID-19 IMPACT ON ONLINE SHOPPING (July 2020),:Aziz -Ur-Rehman, Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University, Shaheed Benazirabad Muhammad Muhammad Kashif Sukkur IBA University Muhammad Kashan Javed Bahauddin Zakariya University.
- Online Shopping Behavior during COVID-19 Pandemic: An Indian Perspective (June 2021) Authors: Amit Ranjan Indian Institute of Information Technology Allahabad Madhvendra Misra Indian Institute of Information Technology Allahabad Jitendra Yadav K L University